

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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THE ROLE OF CORPORATE STRUCTURES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF GLOBAL FINANCIAL RELATIONS

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Abstract. This article describes the role of corporate structures in the development of financial relations in the world. Analysis of data on changes in global macroeconomic indicators and the number of corporate structures and the share of their market capitalization in the world's GDP was carried out. On the basis of the results of the research, proposals and recommendations have been developed on the effective establishment of corporate management of financial relations in corporate structures.

Key words: capitalization, stock exchange, corporate governance, corporate structure, joint stock company, investment attractiveness, investment environment, financial relations, investors, shareholders, corporation.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada jahonda moliyaviy munosabatlar rivojlanishida korporativ tuzilmalar faoliyatining o'рни bayon etilgan. Jahonda makroiqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlar o'zgarishi hamda korporativ tuzilmalar soni hamda ular bozor kapitalizatsiyasining jahonda YAIMdagi ulushining o'zgarishiga oid ma'lumotlar tahlili amalga oshirilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari yuzasidan korporativ tuzilmalarda moliyaviy munosabatlarni korporativ boshqaruvni samarali tarzda yo'lga qo'yish borasida taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kapitalizatsiya, fond birjasi, korporativ boshqaruv, korporativ tuzilma, aksiyadorlik jamiyati, investitsion jozibadorlik, investitsiya muhiti, moliyaviy munosabatlar, investorlar, aksiyadorlar, korporatsiya.

Аннотация. В данной статье описывается роль корпоративных структур в развитии финансовых отношений в мире. Проведен анализ данных об изменении глобальных макроэкономических показателей, а также количества корпоративных структур и доли их рыночной капитализации в мировом ВВП. На основе результатов исследования разработаны предложения и рекомендации по налаживанию эффективного корпоративного управления финансовыми отношениями в корпоративных структурах.

Ключевые слова: капитализация, фондовая биржа, корпоративное управление, корпоративная структура, акционерное общество, инвестиционная привлекательность, инвестиционная среда, финансовые отношения, инвесторы, акционеры, корпорация.

INTRODUCTION

In the experience of developed countries of the world, the main attention is paid to corporate governance relations in ensuring the financial stability of large joint-stock companies, corporations, and structures. In this regard, each structure entering into financial relations tries to achieve financial efficiency through corporate governance, giving priority to the activities of certain structures in its activities. Also, "the priority and relevance of ensuring high growth rates of the national economy by increasing the investment attractiveness of joint-stock companies, attracting foreign strategic investors has led to increased attention to the issues of quality and efficiency of corporate governance" [5]. When analyzing financial relations in corporate structures, we analyze the investment activity of these structures based on financial relations. In this regard, the role and significance of corporate structures in the securities market, which form the basis of their investment activity, are considered.

When considering the analysis of macroeconomic indicators of the investment activity of corporate structures in the world, it is appropriate to analyze a number of indicators. Including:

- the total number of corporate structures, including joint-stock companies, and trends in their changes;
- the volume of market capitalization of corporate structures in the securities market;
- change in the share of market capitalization of corporate structures in the global and domestic GDP in the securities market;
- change in the volume of GDP in the world and in the country;
- indicators of the activities of stock exchanges in the world and in the country;
- indicators of the public offering (IPO) of securities of corporate structures, etc.

Let us consider the analysis of these indicators below.

First, let's analyze the trends in GDP changes in the world over the past 5 years.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The term "corporate governance" was first used by R. Ills [1] to reveal the essence of "the structure and functioning of the corporate system." The concept of "corporate governance" itself has been known for a long time and was used in literature published in the early 20th century.

In particular, the system of corporate relations as a process of applying corporate and private property management was first studied in 1932 in the classical works of American legal scholar A. Berle and economist G. Means [2]. Although the term "corporate governance" was not mentioned in their work, they studied corporate governance as an agency relationship between principals (outsiders, investors) and agents (insiders, managers).

According to the scientific research "The effects of corporate governance mechanisms on the financial leverage-profitability relation: Evidence from Vietnam" conducted by Hanh Song Thi Pham, Duy Thanh Nguyen, "corporate governance is an integrated mechanism that operates in economic activities with the characteristic of a collective structure and ensures the growth of capital value. At the same time, the main attention should be paid to the proper organization of financial relations between large shareholders and minority shareholders [3].

In the research conducted by Z.A. Ashurov on "The Concept and Essence of Corporate Governance," the following is stated: "Corporate governance is a means of reliably guaranteeing and ensuring the return of funds invested by capital suppliers (investors, shareholders) in the corporation, as well as making a single decision to control the rational use and fair distribution of financial resources of the corporation, taking into account their interests" [4].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is based on secondary data obtained from international financial databases, corporate reports, and publications of global financial institutions. The analysis applies comparative, structural, and content analysis methods to examine corporate structures across jurisdictions. Qualitative synthesis and logical generalization are used to identify patterns and assess their influence on the evolution of global financial relations.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to the analysis of changes in macroeconomic indicators in the world, reflected below, the volume of world GDP in 2019 amounted to 87.7 trillion US dollars, and in the post-pandemic period, that is, in 2023, this indicator increased by almost 20 percent, and the total volume of world GDP amounted to 105.0 trillion US dollars (Table 1).

Table 1. Analysis of changes in global macroeconomic indicators [11]

№	Indicators	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
1.	GDP volume, trillion US dollars	87,78	85,27	97,15	100,88	105,0
2.	GDP change, percent	2,6	-3,1	6,2	3,1	4,08
3.	GDP per capita, US dollars.	11 338,2	10 904,1	12 316,1	12 687,7	13,268
4.	Change in GDP per capita, in percent	1,5	-4	5,3	2,3	4,5

It should be noted that the impact of the pandemic that began in 2019 had a negative impact on global GDP growth, which we can see in the fact that in 2020 the GDP growth rate decreased by -3.1 percent compared to 2019. In the subsequent period, due to the complex economic situation and geopolitical struggles in the world, the volume of GDP did not show the forecasted development trend.

Confirmation of the above points can be seen in the volume of GDP per capita. That is, if in 2019 this indicator was 11338.2 US dollars in the world, then we see that the growth rate of this indicator in 2020 decreased by -4.0 percent due to the pandemic and amounted to 10904.1 US dollars. In recent years, due to effective measures taken against the pandemic and management methods, GDP per capita indicators have improved. That is, in 2021 this indicator was 12,316.1 US dollars, in 2022 - 12,687.7 US dollars, in 2023 - 13,268 US dollars.

In terms of countries, the TOP-10 countries with the highest GDP figures in 2023 are (Table 2):

Table 2. TOP-10 countries with the highest GDP figures [12]

No	Country name	GDP volume in 2023, trillion US dollars	Share in world GDP, in percent
1.	USA	26,855	25,54
2.	China	19,374	18,43
3.	Japan	4,410	4,19
4.	Germany	4,309	4,10
5.	India	3,737	3,55
6.	Great Britain	3,159	3,00
7.	France	2,923	2,78
8.	Italy	2,170	2,06
9.	Canada	2,090	1,99
10.	Brazil	2,081	1,98

Among the TOP-10 countries in terms of GDP volume by country, the United States, which is considered a developed country, accounts for more than 25% of the total world GDP. In 2023, the country's GDP amounted to 26 trillion 855 billion US dollars. Following is China, a highly demographic country with a total population exceeding 1 billion 425 million in 2024 [13]. In 2023, GDP reached \$19 trillion 374 billion, representing 18.43 percent of global GDP. Another developed country, Japan, had a GDP of over \$4.4 trillion in 2023, accounting for 4.19% of the world's total GDP.

In addition, among the TOP-10 countries with the highest GDP figures, one of the largest countries of the African continent - India - by the end of 2023 had a GDP of 3 trillion 737 billion US dollars. This country's GDP in the reporting year is significant because it amounted to 3.55 percent of global GDP. According to experts, "due to the effective management of corporate structures in these countries, the growth of these structures in the securities market in 2024-2032 is projected to be more than 12 percent" [15].

At the beginning of this paragraph, in accordance with the sequence of analysis, we will analyze the data on the number of corporate structures listed on the stock exchange listing in the securities market, as well as the change in the share of their market capitalization in global GDP (Table 3).

Table 3. Analysis of data on the number of corporate structures in the world and the change in the share of their market capitalization in global GDP [11]

No	Indicators	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
1.	Number of corporate entities listed on stock exchanges, units	49921	49839	51337	47926	46813
2.	Corporate structures market capitalization, trillion US dollars.	79,41	95,2	111,16	93,69	112,0
3.	Share of market capitalization relative to GDP, %	107,9	133,4	131,8	106,5	106,6

The above Table 3 presents an analysis of data regarding the number of corporate structures worldwide and their market capitalization's share in global GDP. According to it, the number of corporate structures listed on stock exchanges was 49,921 in 2019, 49,839 in 2020, 51,337 in 2021, 47,926 in 2022, and 46,813 in 2023. It should be noted that the number of corporate entities listed on stock exchanges decreased by 6.2% in 2023 compared to 2019.

Also, the capitalization of corporate structures listed by stock exchanges in the securities market in 2019 amounted to 79.4 trillion US dollars, and their share in global GDP reached 107.9 percent. Also, in 2020, the volume of market capitalization increased by almost 20 percent compared to the previous year. This year, the volume of market capitalization amounted to 95.2 trillion US dollars. This indicator amounted to 111.16 trillion US dollars in 2021, which is 40 percent more than in 2019 and 16.7 percent more than in 2020. In 2022, the volume of market capitalization increased by almost 18% compared to 2019, but decreased by 1.5% compared to 2020 and by 15.7% compared to 2021.

This situation can also be explained by the decrease in the number of corporate structures included in the listing this year. Also, in 2022, the market capitalization of corporate structures amounted to 93.69 trillion US dollars. Market capitalization this year amounted to 106.5% of GDP. In 2023, the market capitalization of corporate structures included in the list amounted to 112.0 trillion US dollars, which is 106.6% of global GDP.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on analytical data, it can be said that the role of corporate structures in the development of financial relations in the world is of great importance. In this regard, as can be seen in the example of the world and many developed and developing countries, the share of market capitalization in GDP is significant. However, it can be said that the constant instability of the number of listed corporate structures caused fluctuations in the market capitalization of corporate structures. At the same time, it should be noted that changes in market capitalization and the number of corporate structures included in the list fluctuate against the background of various economic, financial, social, and political situations that have occurred on a global scale. In particular, the coronavirus pandemic that began in 2019, the escalating geopolitical situation in the Middle East and Eurasia, and serious changes in fuel and energy prices are relevant examples.

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